

Studies on Kinetics and Mechanism of Complexation of Iron(III) by Dihydroxamic Acids in Aqueous Acid Media

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The thermodynamics and kinetics of formation of 1 : 1 complexes of Fe^{III} with malono- and succino-dihydroxamic acids (MDH and SDH respectively) in acidic aqueous solution have been studied spectrophotometrically by stopped-flow technique. From the experimental k_{obs} values for approach to equilibrium obtained at different concentrations of acid and the reactants it has been possible to evaluate the rate constants for the formation and dissociation of the complexes involving Fe_{aq}³⁺ and Fe(OH)_{aq}²⁺ as the reacting Fe^{III} species. The results have been compared with corresponding values for reactions of Fe^{III} with benzohydroxamic acid and evidence furnished for an associative mechanism for reaction of Fe_{aq}³⁺ and a dissociative mechanism for reaction of Fe(OH)_{aq}²⁺; complex formation by SDH is faster than by MDH.

Hydroxamic acids are weak organic acids¹ having wide application in analytical chemistry² owing to their ability to form stable complexes with several transition metal ions. Some naturally occurring hydroxamic acids serve as iron(III) specific chelators known as siderophores and are involved in microbial iron transport³. Several of these siderophores characterised so far have the hydroxamate group as the iron binding site^{4,5} which accounts for the biological significance of such complexes⁶⁻⁹. The great affinity of hydroxamate group for iron(III) is also the basis for the use of such substances in the treatment of iron imbalance in human body¹⁰⁻¹², and also in removing excess iron from the body cells. Hence, thermodynamic and kinetic aspects of chelation of iron(III) by hydroxamic acids are worthy of investigation. From results of X-ray crystallographic studies¹³⁻¹⁵ it is known that hydroxamate group behaves as a bidentate (O,O as donors) ligand forming a five-membered chelate ring.

Thermodynamic and kinetic studies on the complexation of iron(III) with benzohydroxamic acid and some *ortho*-substituted benzohydroxamic acids have been reported¹⁶. The present work

is on the thermodynamic and kinetic aspects of complexation of Fe^{III} with two dihydroxamic acids, viz. malonodihydroxamic acid (MDH) and succinodihydroxamic acid (SDH), in aqueous acid media.

Results and Discussion

Evaluation of pK_a values of the ligands :
The stepwise deprotonation of a dihydroxamic acid, H₂L, may be represented by the following equilibria :

The pK_a values for the dihydroxamic acids (H₂L) were evaluated experimentally by Bjerrum's pH-metric method^{17a} with appropriate modification^{17b} under conditions similar to those for kinetic measurements. Using data from the pH-titration curve \bar{n}_H was calculated and therefrom the K_{a1} and K_{a2} values graphically following the procedure of Irving and Rossotti^{18,19}. These values are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF pK_{a1} AND pK_{a2} OF THE LIGANDS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Ligand	Temp.	pK_{a1}	pK_{a2}
	$^{\circ}\text{C}$		
Malonodihydroxamic acid	35	5.80	7.60
	40	5.45	7.00
	45	5.10	6.50
Succinodihydroxamic acid	35	6.45	7.30
	40	6.10	6.90
	45	5.80	6.56

Evaluation of equilibrium constants for formation of the iron(III) hydroxamate complexes in aqueous acid media : The equilibrium constant (Q_1) for the following iron(III)-dihydroxamate complexation reaction was evaluated spectrophotometrically :

$$Q_1 = \frac{[\text{FeL}_{\text{aq}}^+][\text{H}^+]^2}{[\text{Fe}_{\text{aq}}^{3+}][\text{H}_2\text{L}]} \quad (3b)$$

Denoting the molar extinction coefficients of the metal ion, the ligand and the complex by $\epsilon_{\text{Fe}^{3+}}$, $\epsilon_{\text{H}_2\text{L}}$ and ϵ_{FeL^+} respectively, it can be shown that under the experimental conditions, $[\text{H}^+] \gg T_{\text{Fe}} \gg T_{\text{H}_2\text{L}}$, where T_{Fe} and $T_{\text{H}_2\text{L}}$ are the total iron and ligand concentrations respectively, with $\epsilon_{\text{H}_2\text{L}} \approx 0$ at the wavelength used in the measurements,

$$\frac{T_{\text{H}_2\text{L}}}{A_e - A_0} = \frac{1}{\epsilon_{\text{FeL}^+}} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{Q_1 T_{\text{Fe}} \epsilon_{\text{FeL}^+}} \quad (4)$$

where A_e and A_0 are the measured absorbances of the experimental solution at equilibrium and that of the iron(III) solution in absence of the dihydroxamic acid respectively. Hence, the value of the equilibrium constant Q_1 could be evaluated graphically from the linear plot of $T_{\text{H}_2\text{L}}/(A_e - A_0)$ vs $[\text{H}^+]^2/T_{\text{Fe}}$. For the following equilibrium involving $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_{\text{aq}}^{2+}$ which is likely to be present in the solution of Fe^{III} under the experimental conditions,

it can be easily shown that $Q_2 = Q_1/K_h$. Thus, using known K_h values (Table 3) Q_2 values were evaluated (Table 2).

TABLE 2—VALUES OF EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS, Q_1 AND Q_2 AS EVALUATED FROM EQUILIBRIUM DATA (25°) AND KINETIC DATA ($35, 40, 45^{\circ}$)

Ligand	Temp.	Q_1 mol dm^{-3}	$Q_2 = Q_1/K_h$
	$^{\circ}\text{C}$		
Malonodihydroxamic acid	25	0.95 ^a	-
	25	0.94 ^b	537.0
	35	0.70	239.3
	40	0.64	167.7
	45	0.55	110.9
Succinodihydroxamic acid	25	0.94 ^a	-
	25	0.90 ^b	549.5
	35	0.80	275.6
	40	0.76	197.9
	45	0.71	143.8

^aFrom equilibrium data at 25° ; all the others are from kinetic data. ^bExtrapolated value at 25° from kinetic data for 35, 40 and 45° .

Kinetics and mechanism of formation of 1:1 malono- and succino-dihydroxamateiron(III) complexes in aqueous acid media : For kinetic studies the increase in absorbance due to formation of the complex during the reaction at the λ_{max} of the complexes (480 nm for malonodihydroxamic acid and 490 nm for succinodihydroxamic acid) were followed with time. Pseudo-first order conditions were maintained in the formation reaction by keeping the concentration of iron(III) and acid in large excess compared to that of the dihydroxamic acid in the solution. Ionic strength of the experimental solution was adjusted to 1.0 mol dm^{-3} using KNO_3 . The experiments were carried out at three different temperatures ($35\text{--}45^{\circ}$) for evaluation of ΔH^{\ddagger} and ΔS^{\ddagger} values.

The pseudo-first order rate constant (k_{obs}) was found to decrease with increase in $[\text{H}^+]$ and

TABLE 3—VALUES OF K_h , k_1 , k_2 , k_{-1} AND k_{-2} AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Ligand	Temp. °C	$10^3 K_h$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^{-2} k_1$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	$10^{-2} k_{-1}$ dm ⁶ mol ⁻² s ⁻¹	$10^{-3} k_2$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	k_2 dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
Malanodi- hydroxamic acid	35	2.95	4.66 ± 0.14	6.61 ± 0.19	4.92 ± 0.12	20.54 ± 0.62
	40	3.84	6.87 ± 0.17	10.67 ± 0.32	6.38 ± 0.19	38.04 ± 1.14
	45	4.96	10.09 ± 0.30	18.36 ± 0.55	8.17 ± 0.20	73.68 ± 2.21
Succinodi- hydroxamic acid	35	2.95	7.00 ± 0.21	8.61 ± 0.26	5.08 ± 0.15	18.45 ± 0.55
	40	3.84	10.34 ± 0.26	13.61 ± 0.41	7.29 ± 0.22	36.84 ± 1.10
	45	4.96	14.94 ± 0.44	20.96 ± 0.63	9.07 ± 0.27	63.11 ± 1.89

increase with increase in T_{Fe} , and the observed dependence conforms to the following reaction scheme (coordinated aqua-ligands omitted all through for clarity) :

where, $k_1/k_{-1} = Q_1$ and $k_2/k_{-2} = Q_2 = Q_1/K_h$ (8)

In equations (7a) and (7b), FeL^+ is the final product having the dihydroxamic acid dianion (2-) presumably bound as a quadridentate ligand (I and II).

The pseudo-first order rate constant for approach to equilibrium leading to the formation of the monocomplex according to the above scheme, when $[H^+] \gg T_{Fe} \gg T_{H_2L}$ (where $[FeL^+]$ is negligible compared to T_{Fe}), is

$$k_{obs} = T_{Fe} \left\{ \frac{k_1[H^+] + k_2K_h}{K_h + [H^+]} \right\} + \frac{[H^+]}{Q_1} \{k_1[H^+] + k_2K_h\} \quad (9)$$

The plot of k_{obs} vs T_{Fe} at a fixed $[H^+]$ is a good straight-line for each one of the dihydroxamic acids under the experimental conditions (T_{Fe} , 0.001–0.004 mol dm⁻³; T_{H_2L} , 0.0001 mol dm⁻³; $[H^+]$, 0.015 mol dm⁻³; I , 1.0 mol dm⁻³ ($HNO_3 + KNO_3$) with slope equal to $\{k_1[H^+] + k_2K_h\}/\{K_h + [H^+]\}$ and intercept equal to $([H^+]/Q_1)\{k_1[H^+] + k_2K_h\}$. Hence,

$$Q_1 = \{\text{slope/intercept}\} \{(K_h + [H^+])[H^+]\} \quad (10)$$

From this relation the values of Q_1 (Table 2) at three different temperatures were evaluated using literature¹⁶ values of K_h and the $[H^+]$ values for the experimental solutions. The Q_1 values thus obtained at 35, 40 and 45° led to extrapolated value of Q_1 at 25° which was in good agreement with that obtained from equilibrium studies by spectrophotometric method at 25° for each of the dihydroxamic acids (Table 2). Rearrangement of equation (9) leads to

$$\frac{k_{obs}}{\frac{T_{Fe}}{K_h + [H^+]} + \frac{[H^+]}{Q_1}} = k_1[H^+] + k_2K_h \quad (11)$$

The plot of left-hand-side of the above equation vs $[H^+]$ has been found to be a straight-line in each case, from the slopes and intercepts of which k_1 and k_2 values were evaluated using K_h values (evaluated¹⁶ using corresponding ΔH and ΔS values reported in literature²⁰). The reverse rate constants k_{-1} and k_{-2} were evaluated from the values of k_1 , k_2 , Q_1 and K_h (see equations 8). All these rate constants were determined at three different temperatures (35, 40

and 45°) which enabled evaluation of the corresponding activation parameters ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger graphically by making use of Eyring equation as usual²¹. Values of k_1 , k_2 , k_{-1} and k_{-2} at three different temperatures are given in the Table 3. The values of the activation parameters ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger corresponding to k_1 , k_2 , k_{-1} and k_{-2} are given in Table 4. From the results which are given in Table 3, it is seen that the rate of formation of the Fe^{III} complex of succinodihydroxamic acid is faster than that of malonodihydroxamic acid.

From a consideration of the pK_a values of the dihydroxamic acids (H₂L) it follows that under the experimental conditions the concentrations of L²⁻ and HL⁻ in the experimental solution will be insignificant to make any contribution to the overall complexation process involving their reaction with any of the Fe^{III} species. Accordingly, it has been logically proposed that the ligands react in the fully protonated form, H₂L. It is seen that these dihydroxamic acids are much more closely comparable in their acid strength than the parent acids, viz. malonic acid and succinic acid. Consideration of the Q_1' values (where Q_1' is the equilibrium constant for the process $Fe^{3+} + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons FeL^+$; hence $Q_1 = Q_1' K_{a1} K_{a2}$, where K_{a1} , K_{a2} and Q_1 are as defined in equations 1,2 and 3b indicates that the dianion of succinodihydroxamic acid (SDH) forms a relatively more stable complex than that of malonodihydroxamic acid (MDH), whereas the reverse is true for the parent acids²². In the case of malonic and succinic acids, the observed stability

sequence is due to the fact that malonate forms a complex having a six-membered chelate ring whereas in case of succinate the chelate ring is seven-membered. The 1 : 1 complexes formed by these dihydroxamic acids presumably have the structures I and II (*loc. cit.*) where the two hydroxamate moieties are linked by a bridging -CH₂- in the case of MDH and bridging -CH₂-CH₂- in the case of SDH. Hence, there will be less strain in the bridging group in the case of succinodihydroxamic acid than in the case of malonodihydroxamic acid. This is why the observed ratio (present work) Q_1' (SDA) : Q_1' (MDA) is 2.56 at 35° ($I = 1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), while the corresponding ratio for succinate and malonate is only 0.26 under roughly comparable conditions (25°, $I = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$)²³.

It is significant to note that ΔH^\ddagger values corresponding to k_1 are near the range of corresponding values for reaction of Fe^{III} with benzo- and some substituted benzohydroxamic acids¹⁶, and these values are perceptibly lower than the ΔH^\ddagger values for the rate of water exchange of Fe_{aq}³⁺ species ($64.0 \pm 2.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$)²⁴ which is in keeping with associative (I_a) character for this reaction path. However, the ΔH^\ddagger values corresponding to k_2 path are quite comparable to the corresponding value ($42.4 \pm 1.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$)²⁴ for the water exchange reaction of Fe(OH)_{aq}²⁺ species indicating a dissociative (I_d) mechanism for the reaction in the k_2 path. In view of this it is significant that while the k_2 values for these dihydroxamic acids are comparable to

TABLE 4—VALUES OF ACTIVATION PARAMETERS CORRESPONDING TO k_1 , k_2 , k_{-1} , k_{-2} FOR FORMATION AND DISSOCIATION OF 1 : 1 COMPLEXES OF Fe^{III} WITH HYDROXAMIC ACIDS

Ligand	For k_1		For k_2		For k_{-1}		For k_{-2}	
	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
Malanodihydroxamic acid	59.2 ± 1.5	-2.9 ± 0.1	41.4 ± 1.2	-41.1 ± 1.2	75.2 ± 1.1	51.9 ± 1.3	96.2 ± 2.9	91.1 ± 2.7
Succinodihydroxamic acid	58.5 ± 3.5	-1.8 ± 0.1	42.3 ± 1.3	-37.3 ± 1.1	64.7 ± 1.6	20.2 ± 0.5	87.4 ± 2.7	62.3 ± 2.2
Benzohydroxamic acid ^a	57.8 ± 0.8	-39.6 ± 2.5	39.1 ± 0.9	-44.5 ± 2.8	51.5 ± 0.8	-101.6 ± 2.8	74.9 ± 1.1	-18.3 ± 3.7
Av.	58.5 ± 1.9		40.9 ± 1.1					

^aFrom Ref. 16.

the k_2 values for the reactions of benzohydroxamic acid and substituted benzohydroxamic acids, the reactions by the k_1 path being associative in character the k_1 values for the dihydroxamic acids are much higher than that for the aforesaid monohydroxamic acids, as shown in Table 5.

TABLE 5

Hydroxamic acid	k_1	$10^{-3} k_2$	Ref.
	$\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$	$\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$	
Benzohydroxamic acid	4.43	4.59	16
Malonodihydroxamic acid	209.2	2.77	Present work
Succinodihydroxamic acid	316.0	2.96	Present work

Experimental

Iron(III) nitrate solution was prepared from freshly precipitated iron(III) hydroxide (from FeCl_3 solution and NH_3) and pure nitrous-free nitric acid. Iron content of the stock solution was estimated volumetrically as usual²⁵. The free acid content of the stock iron(III) solution was determined by passing an aliquot through Dowex 50W-X8 cation exchanger resin the H^+ -form, titrating total acid in the effluent and deducting there from the acid equivalent of iron(III). The acidity of the solutions were adjusted with standard nitric acid (HNO_3) solution, and KNO_3 was used for the adjustment of ionic strength. Malonodihydroxamic acid ($\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$) and succinodihydroxamic acid ($\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$) were prepared by known methods²⁶, and their purity was checked by melting point (malonodihydroxamic acid, 155° ; succinodihydroxamic acid, 180°) and by elemental (C, H, N) analysis. All the stock solutions were prepared in double-distilled water; second distillation of the water was carried out in all-glass still after adding some KOH and KMnO_4 . All chemicals used were of reagent grade (A.R./G.R.) purity or else purified by standard methods before use.

Spectra of the complexes formed in solution at different acid concentration were recorded using a Carl-Zeiss VSU-2P spectrophotometer (Jena, Germany). Composition of the complex formed

was established by well-known mole ratio method which indicated a 1 : 1 complex formation in solution. A stopped-flow spectrophotometer (Hi-Tech, England, SF-3A) coupled with a transient recorder (Data-Lab, DL 905) and a chart recorder (JJ Lloyds, England, PL-3) system was used for kinetic measurements. The thermostatic arrangement of the stopped flow system enabled carrying out the kinetic runs at constant temperature ($\pm 0.05^\circ$).

A Systronics (India) 335 pH meter with glass electrode in combination with saturated calomel electrode was used for making pH measurements after setting using standard buffers. The electrode system was calibrated as usual for determining the $[\text{H}^+]$ of the solutions from the measured pH values whenever necessary.

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